

The Impossibility of Preventing MEV at the Protocol Layer

Anonymous Submission For Double Blinded Review

Abstract—Maximal Extractable Value (MEV) represents the profit obtainable through transaction ordering manipulation by third parties known as *MEV searchers*, constituting a significant challenge in blockchains. While numerous techniques have been proposed to mitigate MEV extraction, their effectiveness and practicality remain elusive. In this paper, we address a fundamental question: *Is it theoretically impossible to prevent MEV extraction at the protocol layer?* We prove that this is indeed the case, making minimal assumptions about the underlying network and consensus protocol, and making no assumptions about MEV mitigation technique. This yields a more general impossibility result than prior work, as it applies broadly across blockchains without assuming specific MEV mitigation techniques, consensus protocols, application semantics, or adversarial thresholds. In light of this impossibility result, we propose shifting from prevention-focused approaches to risk-based deterrents that increase costs and uncertainty for MEV searchers. Finally, we discuss which solution approaches and combinations are likely to be effective and identify areas requiring further research.

Index Terms—AMM, BFT, Blockchain, DAG, MEV, Prevention

I. INTRODUCTION

Centralized exchange operators control trade order matching but generally adhere to the FIFO (first-in-first-out) rule, giving priority (after price) to trade order arrival time. Manipulating this arrival time ordering would constitute market manipulation, threatening the operator’s reputation and potentially causing market failure [1]. Regulatory oversight exists to investigate suspected manipulation, and the penalties for such actions typically far exceed any potential gains, often including severe consequences such as imprisonment [2]. These factors act as strong deterrents rather than absolute preventive measures in traditional marketplaces.

At first glance, a blockchain appears attractive for decentralizing marketplace operation. In public blockchains, anyone can view transaction contents, inspect ledger state, and even simulate the resulting ledger state once a transaction is executed. However, miners or validators have the authority to decide which transactions to include in a block and their execution order. The ability to both monitor pending transactions and simulate the state changes they are likely to induce gives miners/validators a considerable advantage: by iterating over pending transactions, they can determine a transaction ordering that maximizes their rewards at the application level. They may even inject new transactions and order them strategically, such as through front-running, back-running, or sandwiching [3]–[6], to exploit state changes triggered by pending transactions.

These capabilities give rise to *Maximal Extractable Value* (MEV), also referred to as Miner Extractable Value or

Blockchain Extractable Value [3], [7]. MEV captures the profit obtainable by arbitrarily including, excluding, or reordering transactions within a block [7]. The systematic exploitation of such ordering power, known as *MEV extraction*, is carried out by a range of actors, including miners, validators, sequencers, sophisticated users, and automated bots. They are collectively referred to as *MEV searchers*.

Not all forms of MEV extraction are inherently harmful. In particular, competitive and opportunistic MEV, such as arbitrage, can play a beneficial role by reducing price discrepancies across markets [8].

However, when MEV extraction becomes widespread, persistent, and systematically captured by a small set of actors, its effects change qualitatively. In such settings, MEV extraction places a considerable strain on blockchain ecosystem as a whole, extending well beyond the markets from which MEV is being extracted. It becomes an invisible tax on users, with conservative estimates placing Ethereum MEV extraction at ETH 526,207 (i.e., USD 1.1 billion) between September 2022 and June 2024 [9]. Although recent data suggests MEV from sandwich attacks on Ethereum declined from approximately USD 10 million monthly in late 2024 to USD 2.5 million by October 2025 [10], these estimates exclude the fees MEV-aware users pay block builders for protection against extraction. Beyond direct economic loss, persistent MEV extraction can destabilize blockchains by incentivizing consensus-layer manipulation [11]–[13], increasing network congestion, and accelerating centralization pressures [7], [14], [15].

Detecting market manipulation with certainty is challenging even in centralized exchanges, where regulators rely on non-technical factors such as user intent [16]. This challenge becomes even more complex in blockchains [17]. For instance, node operators in public-permissionless blockchains [18] are pseudonymous and can rejoin the network under a different identity or address if their transaction-order manipulation is detected, eliminating any meaningful reputational risk. Additionally, the pseudonymity and immutability of blockchains make it impractical to roll back transactions or enforce penalties proportional to the gains from manipulation. While requiring blockchain nodes to lock a predefined amount of native tokens (and slashing a portion of those tokens in case of misconduct) appears appealing to ensure good governance, it primarily serves as a deterrent. A rational actor may still choose to misbehave if the potential gains exceed the penalty.

More critically, as we demonstrate later, detecting transaction reordering with certainty in distributed systems is known to be inherently impossible because no canonical transac-

tion order exits. Even in public-permissioned [18] or private blockchains, where the identities of parties are known and reputation is expected to incentivize honest behavior, this limitation enables rational actors to misbehave, especially when MEV can be extracted risk-free [19]–[22].

While transaction-order-related market manipulation still exists in centralized exchanges, its success is inherently uncertain. At best, market manipulators can estimate probabilities and calculate expected outcomes, relying on the committed transaction order aligning with their expectations. Market operators typically have strong incentives not to collude with users to manipulate transaction orders. In contrast, on blockchains, MEV extraction can be virtually risk-free. MEV searchers can collaborate with block builders to enforce a specific transaction sequence without either party facing penalties.

This raises an intriguing question: *Is it fundamentally impossible to prevent MEV extraction at the protocol layer?*

Existing impossibility results focus on specific contexts, such as a particular consensus protocol like Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT) [23], [24], a fairness notion like sender or receiver order fairness [24]–[28], an application like Automated Market Maker (AMM) [29], [30], or an attack like front-running [28]. The framing of these results implies that the source of the impossibility lies within the assumed consensus protocol, proposed solution, or application semantics, leading researchers to pursue alternative approaches in search of stronger MEV mitigation guarantees at protocol layer [31], including radical protocol redesigns [32].

In contrast, in this paper, we seek to answer the above question at a foundational level, unconstrained by any specific MEV detection or prevention technique or application semantics. It is important to highlight that, while the gains from MEV extraction are contingent on application semantics (e.g., the amount of MEV extractable from an AMM depends on the mathematical function defining the relationship between asset pools), the root cause of MEV lies in transaction reordering at the protocol layer. This motivates our choice to model MEV at the mechanism level, rather than through application-specific profit formulas.

Fig. 1 depicts our proof sketch and roadmap. We begin by formalizing a minimal MEV model that decouples transaction inclusion from protocol-enforceable transaction order verification. Next, we demonstrate that network-induced ambiguity in message arrival prevents the protocol from certifying a unique global transaction order, resulting in indistinguishability between honest and malicious reordering behaviors (Theorem 1). Consequently, transaction ordering enforcement alone is insufficient to reliably prevent MEV extraction (Theorem 2), which constitutes the root cause of MEV. Building on this result, we then revisit MEV mitigation from a risk-based perspective and examine which combinations of defenses remain practical and effective in reducing MEV extraction. We make the following research contributions:

- *Impossibility of MEV prevention*: Grounded in the properties of distributed systems, we prove that it is impossible

to prevent MEV extraction at the protocol layer through reliable enforcement of transaction ordering.

- *Risk-based mitigation*: In light of the impossibility, we argue that approaches aimed at making MEV extraction uncertain and economically risky, are more promising. We discuss which solution strategies are likely to be effective and identify areas requiring further research.
- *Effectiveness of combined defenses*: Given that many proposed MEV mitigation strategies employ multiple techniques, we also address the related question: *Are multiple MEV defense mechanisms necessary?*

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: After formalizing our MEV model in Sec. II, we show that transaction reordering is fundamentally indistinguishable and cannot be reliably prevented in Sec. III. Motivated by this, in Sec. IV, we shift to a risk-based view of MEV mitigation and study which combinations of defenses remain viable in Sec. V. We present related work and conclusions in Sec. VI and VII.

II. MODELING MEV

A. MEV Extraction

MEV stems from the discretionary authority that block builders (miners, validators, or sequencers) hold over transaction ordering within a block. Upon submission, user transactions typically enter a public transaction pool before being included in a block, allowing MEV searchers to inspect the pool and strategically include, exclude, or reorder transactions to extract profit. A representative example in AMMs involves a validator inserting their transaction ahead of a large pending trade (front-running) to capitalize on the expected price movement, and optionally following it with another transaction (back-running) to realize gains—a pattern widely known as a *sandwich attack*. We refer the reader to [3] for a survey of real-world MEV exploits.

Such profits are realized entirely on-chain via these strategically positioned transactions. Notably, this form of MEV extraction does not inherently depend on coordination among multiple block builders; a single builder with control over one block is sufficient to capture the MEV opportunities within it. That said, more advanced strategies, such as time-bandit attacks or cross-block arbitrage, may confer probabilistic advantages across multiple blocks or rely on indirect coordination through competitive markets involving specialized MEV searchers and block builders. Since the advent of proposer-builder separation (PBS) [33], MEV extraction is frequently mediated by third-party actors who assemble optimized blocks and compete for inclusion rights, yet the ultimate profit accrues to the block builder who proposes the block.

B. Core Execution Model

We begin by introducing a minimal set of concepts that provide clarity for discussing MEV mitigation approaches and help avoid terminology abuse found in the literature. This aims to allow readers to grasp the broader implications of our impossibility results without being constrained by the varying terminology used in MEV mitigation literature.

Fig. 1. Proof sketch and roadmap.

Definition 1 (Transaction Order). A transaction order is a total or partial sequence over a set of transactions that specifies their relative precedence. Formally, given a set of transactions \mathbf{T} , a transaction order is a relation $\prec_{\subseteq} \mathbf{T} \times \mathbf{T}$ that determines which transactions are considered earlier than others. A transaction order may be locally observed (e.g., arrival at a node) or globally committed (e.g., execution recorded on the ledger).

Definition 2 (Execute). Execution is the process of applying transactions to a ledger state according to a given transaction ordering. Given an initial state \mathbf{S} and an ordered sequence of transactions (t_1, \dots, t_n) , execution deterministically produces a new state \mathbf{S}' , provided all transactions are valid under \mathbf{S} . Execution is state-dependent and may succeed or fail depending on both transaction order and current ledger state.

Definition 3 (Commit). A commit is the act of immutably recording a set of transactions along with sufficient information to derive the execution ordering as part of the ledger history. A transaction is considered committed when its inclusion and relative ordering are accepted by the consensus protocol, subject to protocol-level validation by other nodes. Commitment may precede execution in the sense that the execution order must be derivable from the committed data, but it does not necessarily imply immediate finality.

Under Nakamoto-style consensus, a transaction may be committed to the ledger while remaining vulnerable to reorganization, as blocks in the canonical chain can be replaced with non-zero probability. Thus, a commit does not necessarily imply immediate finality. In contrast, BFT-style protocols provide deterministic finality once commitment is reached.

Our analysis does not depend on a specific notion of finality. The impossibility results concern the indistinguishability of transaction ordering decisions at commitment time, prior to execution, and independent of whether commitment is probabilistic or final. Accordingly, we do not distinguish between tentative and final commitment in the remainder of this paper.

C. Block Builders

In a blockchain, consensus nodes (or peers) are responsible for establishing the global transaction order. They achieve this by proposing blocks that typically contain an ordered set of transactions. To propose a block, a node must first earn the right, such as by solving a cryptographic puzzle in PoW (proof of work) or staking native cryptocurrency and waiting for its turn in PoS (proof of stake). Such a node is typically called a *miner* in PoW and a *validator* in PoS. This role is often split in implementations that follow PBS [33], where a *block builder* determines the transactions and their sequencing within a block, while a *block proposer* tries to append that block to

the canonical chain. Similarly, in Hyperledger Fabric [21], nodes responsible for transaction ordering are called *orderers*. Because our focus is on the entity that selects transactions for inclusion in a block, we adopt the following definition:

Definition 4 (Block builder). A blockchain node or peer that selects a subset of pending transactions from its transaction pool to include in a block.

We deliberately exclude transaction ordering from this definition. Although block builders often determine transaction order in practice, this is not a fundamental requirement. A block builder may instead commit only a subset of transactions in the pool, and their execution order can be derived using a uniform rule applied by all consensus nodes. Such rules range from simple heuristics, such as ordering by transaction hash or sender address, to more complex mechanisms like randomized shuffling based on on-chain or off-chain randomness. Several MEV mitigation proposals are framed around restricting a block builder’s ability to specify or predict commit order, allowing it to only choose the transaction set [20], [22], [34].

Throughout this paper, we use *commitment* in the sense of Definition 3. When discussing designs that “remove ordering power”, we specifically refer to mechanisms where the builder commits only to a *set of transactions*, while the eventual execution order is derived by a uniform rule.

D. Inclusion vs Verification

Not every valid transaction is equally attractive to a block builder. Here, validity refers to syntactic correctness (e.g., proper encoding and valid signatures), rather than successful execution. In public blockchains, block builders retain broad discretion over which pending transactions to include. While transaction fees are an important factor, builders may also prioritize their transactions or directly submitted transactions over those arriving via the P2P network. Conversely, altruistic builders may adopt policies such as FIFO or random selection.

Definition 5 (Block inclusion criteria). The conditions a valid and pending transaction must satisfy to be considered for inclusion in a block.

Consensus protocols may specify network-wide block inclusion criteria. Public-permissionless blockchains typically do not impose such requirements, whereas public-permissioned ones may enforce rules such as a base transaction fee. Additionally, block builders can introduce their criteria, provided they do not conflict with network-wide requirements, for e.g., setting a minimum transaction fee in permissionless networks or applying congestion fees in permissioned ones [19].

Because blockchains operate in a trustless environment, they rely on all nodes verifying each other’s actions. This

verification ensures that transactions within a block are valid and that executing those transactions consistently transitions the ledger from one discrete state to another. Let us call this the block verification criteria:

Definition 6 (Block verification criteria). *The conditions a block and its transactions must meet to be deemed valid by the consensus protocol. These conditions are baked into the blockchain client software, and at a minimum include:*

- 1) Block proposal rights: *The miner or validator must have the right to propose a block. For example, in PoW, the miner must solve the cryptographic puzzle, and in PoS, the block must be signed by the validator selected to produce the next block.*
- 2) Valid transactions and block: *Every transaction and block must be correctly encoded, and their digital signatures must accurately correspond to the associated public key and the respective transaction or block contents.*

Many blockchains enforce additional verifications. A notable example is the requirement that the Merkle root (aka transaction root) correspond to the root node of the Merkle tree built from the ordered list of transaction hashes. Ethereum also verifies that the state root matches the root node of the Merkle tree of all ledger states produced by correctly executed transactions. Nevertheless, these represent secondary validations, as the second condition above, together with a consistent execution order across nodes, is sufficient to prevent divergence in the ledger state.

Crucially, block verification criteria enforces only syntactic correctness and block proposer eligibility. They do not impose constraints on transaction arrival order, selection rationale, or relative precedence among valid transactions. This separation between what is *validated* and what is merely *observed* by nodes forms the basis of our impossibility result.

E. Transaction Reordering and MEV

Given the discretion afforded to block builders, transaction ordering can be exploited to derive additional value, e.g., by delaying earlier transactions (front-running), omitting selected ones (censorship, clogging, or suppression), or injecting strategically positioned transactions such as back-running or sandwiching [3], [4]. To abstract away from specific attack strategies to extract MEV, we define transaction reordering in a protocol-agnostic manner.

Definition 7 (Transaction reordering). *Given a set of valid, pending transactions that satisfy the block inclusion criteria, transaction reordering occurs when the sequence of transactions committed to the ledger differs from the transaction order in which they were originally received by the block builder’s transaction pool.*

Note that reordering is defined with respect to the *committed* sequence, not a transaction’s textual position within a block, allowing models where a block builder commits a transaction set while a protocol-level rule derives the execution order.

It is natural to regard a transaction order as fair when no reordering occurs, e.g., FIFO rule in centralized markets. While some prior work defines fairness as a state where “*it is impossible for any party to include or exclude transactions after observing their contents,*” [4] this notion is impractical because determining causality—whether a new transaction was issued in response to one already seen—is difficult, if not impossible, in a distributed system. In contrast, our definition focuses solely on the block builder’s local view of its transaction pool and the resulting committed sequence, regardless of any transaction sender’s intent.

Daian et al. [35] introduced the term MEV, defining it as “... *value that is extractable by miners directly from smart contracts as cryptocurrency profits.*” Several formulations exist to quantify MEV gains (e.g., [36]–[38]). Although the magnitude of MEV gains is governed by application semantics (e.g., constant-product AMM), transaction reordering at the protocol layer constitutes the fundamental mechanism underlying MEV extraction. As such, our interest lies not in the MEV profits themselves but in the transaction ordering capability that underlies them. Grounded in transaction reordering, we thus model MEV at the mechanism level rather than through application-specific profit formulas, and define the MEV extraction mechanism as follows:

Definition 8 (MEV extraction). *The process by which block builders derive additional value through transaction reordering, beyond standard transaction fees.*

F. Network Effects and Arrival Order

Finally, we highlight a fundamental property of Internet-scale networks that undermines any assumption of a well-defined global transaction arrival order. When blockchain nodes communicate over the Internet via a P2P network, message delivery is policy-driven (e.g., ISP business relationships and asymmetric routing), rather than geometry-driven.

Definition 9 (Triangle inequality violation). *Internet routing is policy-driven rather than geometry-driven. Consequently, the geometric triangle inequality, i.e., $distance(A, C) \leq distance(A, B) + distance(B, C)$, does not necessarily hold for network latency.*

This property can be exploited to play latency games, creating the illusion that one transaction originated before another. For example, see the latencies among three nodes $A \rightarrow B = 50$ ms, $B \rightarrow C = 70$ ms, and $A \rightarrow C = 150$ ms in Fig. 2 (assuming symmetric latencies for simplicity). If A sends a transaction at time t_0 , it reaches B at t_{50} and C at t_{150} . Upon seeing A ’s transaction, B may choose to front-run by issuing a new transaction at t_{60} . This new transaction reaches A and C at t_{110} and t_{130} , respectively. Consequently, for C , B ’s transaction appears before A ’s transaction. Therefore, even without adversarial behavior, different nodes may observe different arrival orders for the same set of transactions, making any protocol-level attempt to certify a unique “correct” arrival order fundamentally fragile.

Fig. 2. Triangle inequality violation in Internet latency. Although direct traffic from A to C takes 150 ms, routing via B takes only 120 ms, illustrating non-geometric network latency.

III. IMPOSSIBILITY OF RELIABLE MEV DETECTION

A. Blockchain Network Assumptions

We assume a P2P network among blockchain nodes with properties typical of large distributed systems. First, there is no global clock accessible to all entities, including transaction senders and block builders, such that they cannot reliably timestamp transaction send or receive times. Further, we assume a *partially synchronous network*, where messages are delivered within a bounded time, but nodes are unaware of the maximum delay [39]. Such a network guarantees only that a message sent by a correct node will eventually arrive at its destination (e.g., reliable multicast in BFT-based consensus). Finally, we assume the network is *asymmetric*, where latencies differ between nodes or even in reverse directions, violating the triangle inequality (see Definition 9).

Public blockchain networks use gossiping to propagate newly arrived transactions and blocks, rather than techniques such as ordered reliable multicast, which are unsuitable for Internet-scale systems. Ordered reliable multicast only establishes a logical global transaction order, which does not necessarily reflect their physical arrival order. Alternatively, gossiping is slow and best-effort, not guaranteeing all transactions reach every node within a time bound. For example, our analysis¹ of Ethereum in 2021 showed that fewer than 60% of the pending transactions reached the transaction pool of the Geth client we hosted (with 50 peer connections) before appearing in the next block.

B. Threat Model

Transaction senders may be honest or strategic, but our focus is on block builders, who can control transaction inclusion and ordering within blocks. Block builders may be honest, rational, or dishonest.

An *honest* block builder follows both the consensus protocol and any prescribed transaction selection or ordering rules, regardless of potential profit. A *dishonest* block builder may arbitrarily deviate from the protocol, including proposing invalid blocks that are expected to be rejected.

In contrast, a *rational* block builder strictly adheres to consensus protocol and block verification criteria, but selectively deviates from non-enforceable behaviors (e.g., transaction ordering) whenever doing so increases the expected profit without introducing detectable protocol violations. We formalize this notion below as the foundation for our analysis.

¹(Link was removed due to double-blind review)

Definition 10 (Rational block builder). A block builder is rational if it follows the consensus protocol and block verification criteria whenever deviation risks block rejection or punishment, but is willing to deviate from prescribed transaction ordering or inclusion behavior whenever such deviation yields strictly higher expected utility and cannot be reliably detected or punished.

Here, block builders can maximize economic utility through transaction inclusion, exclusion, or reordering, while remaining compliant with block verification criteria. They may collaborate with external MEV searchers or submit their transactions to exploit state changes.

We assume that block verification rules do not enforce transaction ordering constraints beyond those required for syntactic and cryptographic validity (see Definition 6).

C. Indistinguishability of Honest vs Dishonest Reordering

Notably, block verification criteria in current blockchains (see Definition 6) impose no constraints on transaction ordering, leaving block builders free to arrange transactions arbitrarily. This unconstrained ability to reorder transactions is the core mechanism underlying MEV extraction. This observation raises a natural question: *Could an ordering rule be incorporated into the block verification criteria to prevent reordering and, by extension, MEV extraction?* The following theorem demonstrates that enforcing such a rule is infeasible.

Theorem 1. For any deterministic ordering rule Π , if there exist two transaction orders: (i) one resulting from honest transaction arrivals, and (ii) one resulting from malicious reordering, then these two orderings are indistinguishable at the protocol level.

Proof (Theorem 1). We argue by contradiction. Suppose there exists a deterministic ordering rule Π that can reliably distinguish between honest transaction arrival order and one resulting from malicious reordering.

In public-permissionless blockchains, high node churn [40] and gossip-based transaction diffusion imply nodes often have partial and non-synchronized views of the transaction pool (these networks aim for eventual consistency). Thus, even among honest nodes, observed arrival orders of pending transactions can differ, and a globally agreeable total ordering need not exist—providing an intuitive proof of the theorem. To avoid relying on this variability, we consider a stronger setting.

Consider a network snapshot immediately after block height h , where n block builders b_1, \dots, b_n are active, all aware of the block at height h , and synchronized on the current transaction pool order. During the inter-block interval, suppose n new transactions t_1, \dots, t_n arrive. Let each block builder b_i receive them in the cyclic order:

$$t_i, t_{i+1}, \dots, t_n, t_1, \dots, t_{i-1},$$

so that b_i is the only builder that observes $t_i \prec t_{i-1}$ (i.e., t_i before t_{i-1}), while all others observe $t_{i-1} \prec t_i$. Consequently, each builder has a different “correct” arrival sequence, yet, no

majority for the entire pending transaction sequence. Pairwise majority comparisons over these transaction arrivals produce

$$t_1 \prec t_2 \prec \dots \prec t_n \prec t_1,$$

a cycle (known as Condorcet cycle [41]); therefore, no majority-consistent total order exists.

Now suppose j -th block builder b_j is dishonest and swaps the adjacent pair it uniquely observed as $t_j \prec t_{j-1}$, publishing instead $t_{j-1} \prec t_j$ in the next block. This produces the identical sequence observed by builder b_{j-1} . Because the ordering rule Π must decide based on observed transaction orders, and there is no majority-consistent total order across the blockchain network, Π cannot distinguish whether b_j reordered transactions or whether its published sequence simply matches an honest builder’s transaction arrival view. Thus, Π cannot reliably detect reordering in this setting.

For concreteness, when $j = 1$, b_1 is the only node that observes $t_1 \prec t_n$, while all others observe $t_j \prec t_{j+1}$. If b_1 publishes $t_n \prec t_1$, then the induced pairwise majorities require $t_j \prec t_{j+1}$ for all j and simultaneously $t_n \prec t_1$, forming the same Condorcet cycle and precluding a globally agreeable total order. Hence, Π cannot reliably identify reordering. This contradicts the assumption that a reliable, deterministic ordering rule Π exists, completing the proof. \square

While it is theoretically possible for all block builders to share an identical pending transaction sequence, such cases are extremely rare. In practice, any distribution of pending transaction sequences between these two extremes (i.e., complete agreement vs entirely distinct views) is possible. Occasionally, a majority transaction sequence may emerge among honest block builders. However, this cannot be leverage to conclusively detect that a builder has manipulated the transaction order; it could simply reflect random variations in transaction arrival. Consequently, no block builder can be identified as dishonest with certainty, rendering “reliable” detection of reordering impossible. A rational block builder can exploit this uncertainty to reorder transactions when advantageous, without being consistently dishonest. If most builders act rationally and compete to reorder transactions for their advantage, they may each propose a unique sequence, further undermining any prospect of a stable majority order.

D. Impossibility of MEV Prevention

The pseudonymity and atomicity inherent to blockchains make prevention a more effective strategy than detection followed by enforcement. The objective, however, is not partial or probabilistic mitigation, but reliable, systematic prevention under worst-case rational (Byzantine) behavior. In particular, if even a single block builder can deviate from the prescribed ordering without producing verifiable evidence of misbehavior, the protocol cannot safely enforce arrival-order correctness.

Control over transaction ordering is the primary mechanism for extracting MEV; thus, eliminating such control could, in principle, prevent MEV. However, the indistinguishability described above introduces unavoidable degrees of freedom in

how transactions may be ordered. These degrees of freedom cannot be fully constrained by the protocol and therefore admit strategic manipulation by rational block builders. As a result, any ordering rule leaves residual opportunities for adversaries to obtain favorable orderings. Consequently, reliably preventing MEV extraction through transaction ordering alone is infeasible. From this, we derive the following theorem:

Theorem 2. *Reliably preventing MEV extraction at the protocol layer of a blockchain solely through the enforcement of transaction orderings is impossible.*

Proof (Theorem 2). MEV extraction occurs when block builders “include, exclude, or reorder pending transactions within a block” [42]. Each of these actions constitutes a form of transaction reordering (see Definition 8).

Suppose a transaction ordering rule Π is proposed as part of the block verification criteria to prevent MEV extraction. For Π to effectively prevent MEV, it must determine transaction ordering in a way that cannot be strategically influenced by block builders or other participants. Any residual ability to influence ordering introduces exploitable opportunities for rational adversaries, which contradicts the objective of reliable, systematic prevention. However, by Theorem 1, no such ordering rule Π can be constructed. Consequently, block builders can strategically manipulate the inputs to Π to obtain favorable orderings. Because such influence over ordering is sufficient to enable MEV extraction, it follows that no transaction ordering rule can eliminate block builders’ ability to extract MEV. Therefore, reliably preventing MEV solely through transaction ordering enforcement at the protocol layer is impossible. \square

Our impossibility analysis assumes no specific consensus protocol, mitigation technique, or application semantics, and thus applies broadly to blockchains. The implications are most evident in blockchains and BFT systems where block builders determine commit order. In directed acyclic graph (DAG) protocols [20], [22], [43], [44], global commit order is established post block creation using deterministic block-ordering rules. However, our result still holds for intra-block transactions, as such rules typically preserve within-block transaction order. Further, block-ordering rule can be circumvented per Theorem 1, where block builders can intentionally omit creating edges to earlier blocks with transactions that interfere with their MEV goals (i.e., reordering), effectively prioritizing newer blocks, see attacks demonstrated in [20], [22]. Therefore, the impossibility extends to DAG protocols.

IV. MAKING MEV RISKY

When transaction ordering is not enforced by block verification criteria, block builders can extract MEV risk free. This is not merely due to the absence of an honest majority, but because one or more rational builders can strategically reorder transactions in ways that prevent convergence to a consistent ordering [19], [20], [22], [25], [28]. Consequently, ordering remains inherently influenceable, and MEV persists even under idealized ordering rules, because such influence cannot be eliminated at the protocol level.

Our impossibility result is more fundamental and broader than prior work [23]–[30], which frames impossibility as a limitation of chosen MEV mitigation strategies. These approaches typically attempt best-effort solutions by detecting some form of majority ordering among honest consensus nodes and, in cases of conflict, resort to including all disputed transactions in the same block and ordering them randomly, alphabetically, or using other heuristics [20], [25]. Fundamentally, these methods rely on the assumption that imposing risk on block builders will deter MEV extraction. However, known attacks exist that allow builders to bypass such ordering rules with high certainty [20], [22], [25], [28].

Practical challenges also arise, including the computational and network overhead of validating ordering rules, the unbounded number of pending transactions that far exceeds limited block size, and the need to define ordering over a countably infinite set [26]. Ultimately, these methods act as deterrents—aiming to make MEV extraction risky (e.g., through potential stake loss or block exclusion from the canonical chain)—rather than true prevention techniques, despite sometimes being presented as such in the literature [4].

We propose that MEV mitigation should embrace a risk-based lens, as this characterizes the de-facto approach of both emerging implementations and academic solutions. The goal is to make it increasingly difficult for a block builder to extract meaningful MEV from vulnerable transactions, e.g., either by complicating reordering or eliminating their profitability.

To plan its MEV attack strategy and exploit transaction reordering effectively, a block builder needs to have visibility into transaction contents. For example, to outbid a pending transaction, the attacker needs to know the bid specified in that transaction. In MEV attacks like sandwiching on an AMM, the attacker must also simulate the resulting ledger state after executing the vulnerable transaction to determine optimal token amounts for front-run and back-run swaps, offered transaction fees, and calculate potential profit. Additionally, the attacker must control the position of these transactions in the committed ordering to maximize gains and avoid becoming a victim of another MEV searcher.

From this perspective, the following strategies emerge to increase the risk associated with MEV extraction:

- *Content concealment*: Hide transaction details from MEV searchers, including block builders, to prevent reliable identification of MEV opportunities. It also hinders accurate estimation of state changes caused by vulnerable transactions, making attack planning and profit estimation significantly harder.
- *Order uncertainty*: Eliminate block builders’ capacity to determine or anticipate transaction commit ordering.

Redesigning DeFi (decentralized finance) applications to be agnostic to transaction ordering (e.g., through batch auctions) has been identified as a viable mitigation approach [4], [6], [45], [46]. However, we set this aside in this paper, given that it does not constitute a protocol-level solution and cannot be generalized to all use cases.

At first glance, implementing one of the above strategies may seem sufficient to make MEV extraction risky. For example, concealing transaction content would make it harder for MEV searchers to identify vulnerable transactions, plan attacks, and calculate potential gains. However, transactions inherently reveal metadata such as sender and receiver addresses, client IP addresses, transaction fees, and historical activity patterns to block builders. For example, knowing the target smart contract address is sufficient to prioritize a transaction and displace subsequent ones in initial coin offerings, liquidation in lending protocols [3], and oracle reporting in prediction markets. Identifying the target AMM of a pending transaction enables attackers to leverage on-chain data for arbitrage opportunities. Thus, even when core transaction details are concealed, metadata leakage supplies actionable information that can inform MEV extraction strategies. Consequently, while cryptographic hiding is deterministic, metadata leakage gives rise to probabilistic MEV vectors.

Content concealment creates an information gap not only for MEV seekers but also for users. This reduces a market’s transparency, as users must submit transactions without knowing the latest market state due to the time lag between committing concealed transactions and later revealing their contents to execute and update the ledger state. State staleness elevates transaction failure rates by introducing discrepancies between the ledger state observed at issuance and the actual state at execution. For an AMM, this is analogous to hiding the trade order book and latest pool volumes that determine prices. Such opacity inevitably increases risk for users. While blind-actions, sealed bids, and dark pools constitute potential market redesign approaches, they are broadly acknowledged as inefficient due to their adverse effects on price discovery.

Alternatively, the transaction *order uncertainty* strategy takes away block builder’s ability to anticipate the final commit ordering with certainty. However, this merely introduces uncertainty regarding the success rate and potential gains of an MEV attack. In use cases like domain name registration, bug bounty, and liquidation in lending protocols, an attacker’s sole requirement may be to ensure its transaction is the only one in a block, effectively making it the first transaction for a vulnerable DeFi application. If transaction content remains visible, it is easier for an attacker to replicate transactions and exclude competing ones from blocks with certainty, independent of the eventual execution and commit ordering.

Therefore, while each strategy individually increases uncertainty for block builders, their combination is necessary to protect a broad range of DeFi applications and raise the overall risk of MEV extraction. Even combined, these strategies can only increase uncertainty; they cannot eliminate MEV extraction entirely. This reinforces the need to adopt a risk-based approach from the outset, rather than treating it as an afterthought once a mitigation technique proves unreliable.

V. REVISITING MEV REDUCTION APPROACHES

The substantial body of MEV mitigation research primarily adopts one or both of the risk-enhancement strategies dis-

TABLE I
MEV MITIGATION STRATEGIES EVALUATED UNDER THE ORDERING IMPOSSIBILITY RESULTS.

MEV mitigation approach	Enforces global order	Detects reordering	Resilient to network ambiguity	Relation to Thm. 1-2	Implications under impossibility
Proposer-builder separation	None	None	No	Evades	Reallocates MEV via off-chain auctions; builder ordering remains unconstrained and user-facing MEV persists.
Fair ordering	Partial	Pairwise-only	No	Violates	Weakened fairness enforcement fails due to arrival ambiguity and Condorcet cycles. MEV persists.
Commit-reveal (content concealment)	Delayed	Post-reveal only	Partial	Evades	Hides content temporarily, but certain forms of MEV returns after reveal. May harm liveness and atomicity.
Order uncertainty (via randomization)	None	None	Partial	Accepts	Accepts ordering indistinguishability and randomizes order to bound MEV, but cannot prevent set manipulation.
TEE-based ordering enforcement	External	Local attestation	Yes	Shifts assumptions	Outsources ordering to trusted hardware, shifting security to enclave integrity and non-collusion.
Advanced cryptography (ZKP, FHE, and MPC)	None	None	Yes	Accepts	Preserves ordering ambiguity, liveness, and atomicity with content concealment. Immature and costly at scale.
MEV-aware application design	Application-specific	Application-specific	Yes	Orthogonal	Mitigates MEV via application redesign, but is non-portable and costly to deploy.

cussed earlier [3], [4], [6], [31], [46], [47]. In Table I, we evaluate how major classes of these solutions align with our impossibility result, with the goal of identifying approaches that hold the greatest promise for future research. Prior MEV surveys [3], [4], [6], [31], [46], [47], though rich in taxonomic coverage across many dimensions (e.g., security, decentralization, cost, and latency), have not considered the positioning of existing approaches relative to a protocol-layer impossibility result, a dimension we introduce here for the first time.

Proposer-Builder Separation. PBS decouples two roles: the *block proposer*, who holds the right to propose the next block, and the *block builder*, who constructs block contents [33], [48]. Rather than proposers directly assembling MEV-maximizing blocks, PBS establishes an off-chain marketplace wherein builders construct transaction bundles and submit fee bids to proposers. Rational builders engage in competitive bidding [49], [50], progressively increasing fees to secure selection. A builder bidding too conservatively to retain MEV risks auction failure (i.e., introduce order uncertainty), while competition incentivizes bidding near expected MEV extraction, theoretically driving net builder profits toward zero.

PBS is often viewed as a democratizing mechanism because, in principle, any party can participate in the bidding process. More importantly, it increases the economic risk for MEV searchers to the point where sustained MEV extraction may become unprofitable. Several PBS variants are currently deployed in practice (though not yet standardized at the protocol level), and recent reductions in measured monthly MEV extraction can partially be attributed to these mechanisms [10].

However, PBS fails to eliminate indirect tax imposed on users. To avoid MEV extraction, users pay block builders for protection, such as through private pool submissions. These arrangements are unenforceable without regulation. Consequently, while PBS constitutes a risk-based mechanism that may discourage MEV extraction, it neither resolves the user-facing problem nor guarantees complete MEV prevention.

Fair Ordering. This MEV mitigation class enforces network-wide transaction ordering according to specified fairness criteria. Our impossibility result has direct implications for these approaches. Consequently, solutions adopt weakened

fairness definitions, placing conflicting transactions within the same block and applying random or heuristic ordering. Because attackers can readily generate conflicting transaction orders [19], [20], [22], [25], [28], these ordering rules are circumventable with high probability, introducing minimal risk for MEV searchers. Alternative proposals employ off-chain fair ordering for domain-specific applications such as AMMs or registries. However, this architecture resembles centralized market design, combining off-chain ordering with on-chain settlement, providing limited decentralization advantages.

Commit and Reveal. This content-concealment strategy (aka content-agnostic ordering) proceeds in two phases. Initially, users commit transactions without disclosing details, typically via recording hashes or encrypted payloads. Subsequently, content is revealed either through user-submitted transactions matching committed hashes, decryption key disclosure, or automated revelation via time-lock puzzles, timed commitments, or threshold cryptographic schemes involving a committee of blockchain nodes. This mechanism elevates MEV searchers’ risk across applications like AMMs by obstructing attack strategy formulation and precise profit calculation. However, several limitations affect users: the commit-reveal time lag prevents visibility into the effective ledger state and breaks atomicity, premature timeouts can expose content immutably, and unfavorable revealed states may incentivize users to withhold revelation leading to application-level deadlocks. While on-chain, committee-based threshold signatures can automate key generation, this introduces trust assumptions regarding committee non-collusion, itself a risk-based security model.

Order Uncertainty. This risk-based approach decouples transaction selection from commit-order determination: block builders choose transaction sets while randomization mechanisms prevent them from controlling or anticipating commit sequences. On-chain random seed generation following block inclusion can be achieved through mechanisms such as Ethereum PoS’s RANDAO [32], [51], which derives entropy from attestation committee signatures. However, the full pipeline—block construction, attestation, random seed generation, transaction shuffling, execution, and ledger commitment—cannot complete within a single block, impos-

ing inter-block latency. Alternatively, TEEs (trusted execution environments) can enforce and attest verifiable random ordering [52]. Yet, both approaches suffer from a critical vulnerability: block builders can selectively censor and include transactions to manipulate the shuffling pool [20], [22], [53]. Given limited research on commit-order-execute models, innovation opportunities remain, particularly considering theoretical and practical arguments for randomization-based fairness [54].

Zero-knowledge proofs (ZKPs) have achieved widespread adoption in blockchains, particularly within Layer-2 architectures. However, other emerging privacy-preserving technologies such as fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) and secure multi-party computation (MPC) remain less mature and require further research before they can be integrated with minimum disruption to existing execution engines. Just as the development of zkEVMs took several years, these technologies necessitate substantial technical advancement. FHE presents particular promise for transaction-content concealment, as it enables continued real-time ledger state visibility while protecting sensitive transaction data, e.g., AMM pool balances could remain publicly observable while individual swap amounts remain encrypted. MPC has demonstrated utility in commit-reveal protocols, enabling trusted and privacy-preserving disclosure of transaction inputs [31].

MEV-aware application design offers another mitigation approach [4], [6], [45], [46], though it lacks general applicability and is beyond our scope. For instance, they can combine with FHE or MPC for secure aggregation of encrypted swap orders in AMMs. However, their adoption necessitates significant DeFi protocol redesign, spanning relatively straightforward modifications (e.g., slippage and transaction fee limits) to fundamental architectural changes such as blind auctions or batch-execution. Also, MEV prevention demands deep understanding of the underlying blockchain architecture to address platform-specific weaknesses, making solutions non-portable.

VI. RELATED WORK

Beyond existing MEV mitigation solutions surveyed in [3], [4], [6], [31], [46], [47], we focus on prior impossibility results directly related to our contribution.

Kelkar et al. [23] introduced the notion of *transaction order fairness* for BFT systems, defined as: if at least an γ fraction of nodes received transaction t_1 before t_2 , then all honest nodes must output t_1 before t_2 . By mapping the fairness problem to a Condorcet cycle [41], they proved that no protocol can simultaneously achieve consistency, liveness, and receive-order fairness, even in the absence of adversaries. Their model assumes nodes are always active and known, and that clients broadcast transactions to all nodes. Kursawe [24] adopted the same fairness definition under a similar network model with t Byzantine nodes ($n = 3t + 1$), and also leveraged Condorcet cycles to demonstrate impossibility. Vafadar et al. [25] also showed that even a single dishonest attacker can induce a Condorcet cycle by submitting two additional transactions. Park et al. [28] established a front-running prevention impossibility result using a comparable network model and Condorcet cycle.

Ciampi et al. [27] argued that receiver-order fairness fails to capture input causality and proposed *sender-order fairness*. Under a network model with a global clock, timestamped transactions, and PoW consensus, they used the universal composition framework to prove that achieving sender-order fairness is infeasible in networks with bounded delays.

Wadhwa et al. [30] proved the impossibility of enforcing any order policy when all parties are rational, showing that collusion among rational nodes can deniably violate ordering rules. Ferreira and Parkes [29] provided an AMM-specific proof demonstrating that for any order policy, there exists a transaction set that enables extracting risk-free profit.

In contrast, our impossibility result does not assume a specific order policy, consensus protocol, transaction information model, or any majority of dishonest or rational actors. Consequently, prior results offer only protocol-specific insights, whereas our result establishes a fundamental impossibility of preventing transaction-order manipulation in blockchains.

VII. CONCLUSION

We study MEV mitigation from a foundational perspective, showing that its root cause lies in inherent distributed-systems properties rather than specific protocol designs or fairness notions. We prove that protocol-level mechanisms cannot distinguish network-induced reordering from strategic manipulation, implying that arrival-order enforcement at the protocol layer cannot guarantee MEV prevention. Our result extends to blockchains, BFT protocols, and DAGs with transaction reordering capabilities. This impossibility motivates a shift from prevention to risk-based deterrents that increase the uncertainty and cost of MEV extraction. We leave to future work whether this impossibility extends to Layer-2 systems.

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